

Solving a simple 2D elasticity problem using the finite element method by means of constant strain triangular elements

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SUMMARY

This manuscript aims to show how a simple elasticity problem can be solved using the finite element method by means of constant strain triangular elements. This paper does not intend to explain the finite element method formulation, only its practical application. It shows how the element's geometric moment matrix is constructed, and corresponding shape functions and partial derivatives. It is also presented the construction of the stiffness matrix at the element level and its global assemblage. Afterwards, a swift construction of the global force vector is presented, and then how the displacement constraints can be imposed using a direct technique. Finally, the global system of equations is established and solved, and the variable fields are obtained: displacement, strain and stress fields. Afterwards, in order to show the FEM's dependency on the mesh, the convergence test is shown. In the end, a pedagogic FEM routine is delivered, and the final conclusions and remarks are presented.

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1. BRIEF FEM FORMULATION

1.1. Introduction

In the literature it is possible to find several documents describing the finite element method (FEM) formulation with detail. The bibliography of this manuscript shows some of those documents.

Developed in the last years of the 1950's, FEM is an interpolation technique capable to interpolate any variable field at interest points within a known domain. The procedure divides (discretizes) the solid domain in elementary parts - the elements - as figure 1 shows. These elements are constituted by nodes, and they can show several shapes and configurations. The most common ones for 2D and 3D analyses are shown in figure 2.

FEM can be applied to several science fields (engineering, physics, chemistry, mathematics, biology, etc.). In this manuscript, FEM is applied to a 2D elasticity problem, considering a linear elastic material and small strains.

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Figure 1. Example of a discretization using 2D plane triangular elements.

Figure 2. Examples of some of the most popular 2D and 3D finite elements used in FEM.

1.2. 2D elasticity

For elasticity problems, it is possible to apply the principle of virtual work to establish the system of equations. Therefore, consider the solid domain Ω , with a body force \mathbf{b} , bounded by a surface boundary Γ , submitted to external forces $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$, on the natural boundary Γ_t , and displacement constraints at the essential boundary Γ_u . The virtual work principle, in which, the internal work (W_{int}) is equal to the external work (W_{ext}), can be expressed as,

$$W_{int} = W_{ext} \Rightarrow \int_{\Omega} \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \cdot d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_t} \delta \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} \cdot d\Gamma, \quad (1)$$

being the virtual displacement represented as $\delta \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I)$, and $\delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the corresponding virtual strain. Since this manuscript deals with a 2D elasticity problem, the strain field $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ can be defined as,

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{du}{dx} \\ \frac{dv}{dy} \\ \frac{du}{dy} + \frac{dv}{dx} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d}{dx} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{d}{dy} \\ \frac{d}{dy} & \frac{d}{dx} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ v(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I), \quad (2)$$

being $u(\mathbf{x}_I)$ and $v(\mathbf{x}_I)$ the Cartesian components of the displacement of interest point \mathbf{x}_I . Assuming a linear elastic isotropic material, the stress field can be obtained applying the generalized Hooke's law:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{C} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E} & -\frac{\nu}{E} & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu}{E} & \frac{1}{E} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{2(1+\nu)}{E} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

being \mathbf{C} the material constitutive matrix, E the Young's modulus and ν the Poisson's ratio.

1.3. FEM shape functions - 3 nodes triangular elements

Consider the triangular element represented in figure 3. The 3 nodes of the represented element have the following Cartesian coordinates:

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \begin{Bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{x}_j = \begin{Bmatrix} x_j \\ y_j \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{x}_k = \begin{Bmatrix} x_k \\ y_k \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Figure 3. Generic 2D triangular element.

The shape functions of this simple triangular element, for a generic interest point \mathbf{x}_I inside the element, can be found with:

$$\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{G}^{-1} = \{1 \quad x_I \quad y_I\} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_i & y_i \\ 1 & x_j & y_j \\ 1 & x_k & y_k \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = \{1 \quad x_I \quad y_I\} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} g_{11} & g_{12} & g_{13} \\ g_{21} & g_{22} & g_{23} \\ g_{31} & g_{32} & g_{33} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

being \mathbf{p} the polynomial basis and \mathbf{G} the element's geometric moment matrix. Equation 5 allows to write:

$$\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \{g_{11} + g_{21} \cdot x_I + g_{31} \cdot y_I \quad g_{12} + g_{22} \cdot x_I + g_{32} \cdot y_I \quad g_{13} + g_{23} \cdot x_I + g_{33} \cdot y_I\} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \{N_i(\mathbf{x}_I) \quad N_j(\mathbf{x}_I) \quad N_k(\mathbf{x}_I)\} \quad (7)$$

With the shape functions it is possible to interpolate the any variable field inside the element. Thus, assuming that all the nodal displacement components are known,

$$\mathbf{u}_i = \begin{Bmatrix} u_i \\ v_i \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{u}_j = \begin{Bmatrix} u_j \\ v_j \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{u}_k = \begin{Bmatrix} u_k \\ v_k \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

it is possible to interpolate the displacement field at interest point \mathbf{x}_I :

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{Bmatrix} u(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ v(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{H} \cdot \mathbf{u}_e = \begin{bmatrix} N_i(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & N_j(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & N_k(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 \\ 0 & N_i(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & N_j(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & N_k(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u_i \\ v_i \\ u_j \\ v_j \\ u_k \\ v_k \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

1.4. Discrete system of equation

After the construction of the shape functions, it is possible to establish the system of equations. First, the interpolated displacement $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I)$ obtained in equation 9 is back substituted into equation 2.

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d}{dx} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{d}{dy} \\ \frac{d}{dy} & \frac{d}{dx} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} N_i(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & N_j(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & N_k(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 \\ 0 & N_i(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & N_j(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & N_k(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u_i \\ v_i \\ u_j \\ v_j \\ u_k \\ v_k \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

leading to,

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{dN_i}{dx} & 0 & \frac{dN_j}{dx} & 0 & \frac{dN_k}{dx} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{dN_i}{dy} & 0 & \frac{dN_j}{dy} & 0 & \frac{dN_k}{dy} \\ \frac{dN_i}{dy} & \frac{dN_i}{dx} & \frac{dN_j}{dy} & \frac{dN_j}{dx} & \frac{dN_k}{dy} & \frac{dN_k}{dx} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u_i \\ v_i \\ u_j \\ v_j \\ u_k \\ v_k \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u}_e. \quad (11)$$

The deformability matrix is defined by \mathbf{B} , and performing the partial derivatives of the shape functions presented in equation 6, it is possible to understand that, for the 3-nodes triangular element, the deformability matrix \mathbf{B} is a constant value matrix:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I)}{dx} = \{g_{21} \quad g_{22} \quad g_{23}\}, \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I)}{dy} = \{g_{31} \quad g_{32} \quad g_{33}\}, \quad (13)$$

therefore,

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{B}_e = \begin{bmatrix} g_{21} & 0 & g_{22} & 0 & g_{23} & 0 \\ 0 & g_{31} & 0 & g_{32} & 0 & g_{33} \\ g_{31} & g_{21} & g_{32} & g_{22} & g_{33} & g_{23} \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Developing the virtual work principle presented in equation 1, it is possible to write:

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta (\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u})^T \cdot (\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u}) \cdot d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \delta (\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u})^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \cdot d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_t} \delta (\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u})^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} \cdot d\Gamma \quad (15)$$

which leads to:

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u} \cdot d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \cdot d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_t} \delta \mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} \cdot d\Gamma \quad (16)$$

$$\delta \mathbf{u}^T \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot d\Omega \cdot \mathbf{u} = \delta \mathbf{u}^T \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \cdot d\Omega + \delta \mathbf{u}^T \int_{\Gamma_t} \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} \cdot d\Gamma \quad (17)$$

Its final form represents the system of equations:

$$\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{f}_b + \mathbf{f}_t \quad (18)$$

in which \mathbf{K} , \mathbf{u} , \mathbf{f}_b and \mathbf{f}_t are the global stiffness matrix, the global displacement field, and the global body and external force vectors, respectively. The discretization procedure allows to obtain these entities using a numerical integration:

$$\mathbf{K} = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot d\Omega = \sum_{I=1}^{N_Q} \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \hat{\omega}_I \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_b = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \cdot d\Omega = \sum_{I=1}^{N_Q} \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \cdot \hat{\omega}_I \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_t = \int_{\Gamma_t} \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} \cdot d\Gamma = 0 = \sum_{J=1}^{n_Q} \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_J)^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} \cdot \hat{\omega}_J \quad (21)$$

Variable N_Q represents the number of integration points on the solid domain and n_Q is the number of integration points along the traction surface Γ_t . The integration weight (volume) of such integration points is represented by $\hat{\omega}$.

Since in this manuscript only 3-nodes elements with constant strain are being considered, only one integration point is being considered by element, and its corresponding integration weight is the volume of the element: $V_e = A_e \cdot h_e$, being h_e the thickness of the element and A_e the area of the element. Thus, the stiffness matrix of each element can be calculated with:

$$\mathbf{K}_e = \mathbf{B}_e^T \cdot \mathbf{C}_e \cdot \mathbf{B}_e \cdot V_e \quad (22)$$

If all the local matrices \mathbf{K}_e are already written in the global format, the assemblage is straightforward:

$$\mathbf{K} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} \mathbf{K}_i \quad , \quad (23)$$

being n_e the number of elements. The final system of equations can then be presented as,

$$\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{f} \quad , \quad (24)$$

being \mathbf{K} the global stiffness matrix and \mathbf{f} the global force vector, which are obtained after assembling all the element stiffness matrices \mathbf{K}_e and element force vectors \mathbf{f}_e , respectively. Solving the system of equations, allows to obtain the displacement field \mathbf{d} ,

$$\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{K}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{f}, \quad (25)$$

Since the FEM shape functions possess the delta Kronecker properties, i.e. FEM shape functions are interpolating functions, it is possible to apply the direct imposition technique to enforce the nodal displacement constraints. Thus, if node n_i has its Ox degree of freedom constrained with an enforced displacement \bar{u} it is possible to impose such displacement constraint with:

$$\begin{cases} K_{2i-1,j} = 0, & \text{for } j = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 2N\} \\ K_{2i-1,2i-1} = 1 \\ f_{2i-1,1} = \bar{u} \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

On the other hand, if it is the Oy degree of freedom constrained with an enforced displacement \bar{v} ,

$$\begin{cases} K_{2i-0,j} = 0, & \text{for } j = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 2N\} \\ K_{2i-0,2i-0} = 1 \\ f_{2i-0,1} = \bar{v} \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

After obtaining the displacement field, it is possible to apply equations 10 and 3 to calculate the strain and stress fields.

2. 2D EXAMPLE

Consider the problem domain represented in figure 4. The structure is submitted to the loads and displacement constraints indicated. Assuming a plane stress, consider the mechanical properties indicated in table I.

Figure 4. Proposed 2D example.

Using the four triangular elements of constant strain (3-nodes plane elements) indicated in figure 4, describe with detail, and obtain and represent the following matrix entities assuming the plane stress state:

Elements	Material	Thickness (h)	Young's Modulus (E)	Poisson's coefficient (ν)
e1	Material 1	2 mm	210 GPa	0.31
e2, e3, e4	Material 2	1 mm	70 GPa	0.27

Table I. Problem's data.

- (a) The matrix of nodal coordinates;
- (b) The matrix of elements;
- (c) The matrix of integration points and respective weights (volumes);
- (d) The material constitutive matrix for each element/integration point;
- (e) The shape functions and respective spatial derivatives for each element/integration point;
- (f) The local stiffness matrix of each element (already represented in its global configuration [12x12]);
- (g) The global stiffness matrix of the structure after assembly;
- (h) The global vector of nodal forces;
- (i) The global stiffness matrix and global nodal force vector after the application of boundary conditions using the direct imposition technique;
- (j) The displacement vector;
- (k) The strain state of each element/integration point;
- (l) The stress state of each element/integration point;

The order of the questions lead to the direct solution of the problem. Nevertheless, an alternative algorithm of a 2D elasticity problem can be summarized as follows:

1. Pre-processing.
 - (a) Define the nodal mesh - Cartesian coordinates and indexing.
 - (b) Define the elements - indexing each node to a specific element (element matrix).
 - (c) Define the material properties of each element.
 - (d) Establish the essential boundary and constraints.
 - (e) Establish the natural boundary and external forces direction and magnitudes.
2. Stiffness matrix of each element.
 - (a) Construct the geometric matrix and its inverted version - equation 5.
 - (b) Obtain the partial derivatives of the shape functions and build the deformability matrix - equation 14.
 - (c) Construct the element's constitutive material matrix - equation 3
 - (d) Calculate the area and volume of the element.
 - (e) Calculate the element's stiffness matrix - equation 22.
3. Assemblage of the stiffness matrix of each element into a global stiffness matrix.
4. Construction of the force vector.
5. Imposition of the displacement constraints - equation 27.

6. Construction the system of equations and calculate its solution - equation 25.
7. Obtain the strain field, calculating for each element the strain Cartesian components - equation 11.
8. Obtain the stress field, calculating for each element the stress Cartesian components - equation 3.

2.1. Matrix of nodal coordinates

An array will be constructed containing the Cartesian coordinates of each node. Line 1 is for the x coordinate, line 2 is for the y coordinate and line 3 is for the z coordinate. The columns respect the nodal sequence. The first column is for node 1, the second column for node 2, and so on.

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} 10 & 10 & 0 & 30 & 60 & 60 \\ 0 & 50 & 70 & 70 & 50 & 70 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

2.2. Matrix of elements

It is necessary to indicate which nodes form each element. For instances, element 1 is formed by nodes 1, 2 and 3, and element 2 is formed by nodes 2, 3 and 4. It is necessary to build a matrix with this information. Thus, the lines are associated with the elements (line 1 for element 1, line 2 for element 2, and so on), and the columns are associated with the relative position of each node within the element. Column 1 is for node n_i of the corresponding element, and columns 2 and 3 are for nodes n_j and n_k , respectively.

$$\mathbf{e}_{mat} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 4 & 5 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

2.3. Element's stiffness matrix

This block contains the answer to the questions related with: the matrix of integration points and respective weights (volumes); the material constitutive matrix for each element/integration point; the shape functions and respective spatial derivatives for each element/integration point; the local stiffness matrix of each element (already represented in its global configuration [12x12]);

First, it is necessary to build some matrices related with the mechanical properties of each element. For example, an array for the Young's modulus (\mathbf{Y}), another for the Poisson's ratio (\mathbf{P}), and another for the thickness (\mathbf{h}) of each element:

$$\mathbf{Y} = \begin{Bmatrix} 210000 \\ 70000 \\ 70000 \\ 70000 \end{Bmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{P} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.31 \\ 0.27 \\ 0.27 \\ 0.27 \end{Bmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{h} = \begin{Bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

These arrays follow the same order of the element matrix. The first line is for element 1, the second line is for element 2, and so on. Since this problem is being addressed in [mm], the Young's modulus has to be considered in MPa.

2.3.1. Element 1

First, the corresponding nodes n_i , n_j and n_k forming the element are called from matrix \mathbf{e}_{mat} . Thus, it is created the variable e_i to define the current element. In this case: $e_i = 1$, because it is being calculated element 1.

$$n_i = (e_i, 1) = 1; \quad n_j = (e_i, 2) = 2; \quad n_k = (e_i, 3) = 3; \quad (31)$$

then, the nodal coordinates are recovered:

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{X}(1 : 3, n_i) = \begin{Bmatrix} 10 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{x}_j = \mathbf{X}(1 : 3, n_j) = \begin{Bmatrix} 10 \\ 50 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{X}(1 : 3, n_k) = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 70 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (32)$$

Afterwards, knowing that the thickness of the element is $h_e = \mathbf{h}(e_i, 1)$ the volume of the element is calculated:

$$\mathbf{v}_{ij} = \mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i ; \quad \mathbf{v}_{ik} = \mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{x}_i ; \quad A_e = \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{v}_{ij} \times \mathbf{v}_{ik}\| ; \quad V_e = A_e \cdot h_e = 500 \text{mm}^3 \quad (33)$$

which corresponds to its weight. The theoretical position of the integration point is the centre of the element:

$$\mathbf{x}_I = \frac{1}{3} (\mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{x}_j + \mathbf{x}_k) = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \left[\begin{Bmatrix} 10 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} 10 \\ 50 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 70 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \right] = \begin{Bmatrix} 6.667 \\ 40 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (34)$$

then, the geometric moment matrix \mathbf{G} can be calculated using the nodal coordinates,

$$\mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_i & y_i \\ 1 & x_j & y_j \\ 1 & x_k & y_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 10 & 0 \\ 1 & 10 & 50 \\ 1 & 0 & 70 \end{bmatrix} \quad (35)$$

and its corresponding inverted version:

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{G}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} g_{11} & g_{12} & g_{13} \\ g_{21} & g_{22} & g_{23} \\ g_{31} & g_{32} & g_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.40 & -1.40 & 1.00 \\ -0.04 & 0.14 & -0.10 \\ -0.02 & 0.02 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (36)$$

The shape functions can now be calculated in any interest point inside the element using equation 6. For example, they can be calculated at the integration point:

$$\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{Bmatrix} N_i(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ N_j(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ N_k(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{Bmatrix}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} 1.40 - 0.04 \cdot 6.667 - 0.02 \cdot 40 \\ -1.40 + 0.14 \cdot 6.667 + 0.02 \cdot 40 \\ 1.00 - 0.10 \cdot 6.667 + 0 \cdot 40 \end{Bmatrix}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.333 \\ 0.333 \\ 0.333 \end{Bmatrix}^T \quad (37)$$

More important are the partial derivatives of the shape function, that can be obtained with equation 12 and 13,

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I)}{dx} = \begin{Bmatrix} g_{21} \\ g_{22} \\ g_{23} \end{Bmatrix}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} -0.04 \\ 0.14 \\ -0.10 \end{Bmatrix}^T ; \quad \frac{d\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I)}{dy} = \begin{Bmatrix} g_{31} \\ g_{32} \\ g_{33} \end{Bmatrix}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} -0.02 \\ 0.02 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}^T \quad (38)$$

which allow to obtain the deformability matrix, from equation 14:

$$\mathbf{B}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.04 & 0 & 0.14 & 0 & -0.10 & 0 \\ 0 & -0.02 & 0 & 0.02 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.02 & -0.04 & 0.02 & 0.14 & 0 & -0.10 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (39)$$

This deformability matrix arranged at its local setting, for nodes n_i , n_j and n_k . It is possible to arrange such deformability matrix in the global setting, knowing that node n_i corresponds to node n_1 , node n_j corresponds to node n_2 and node n_k corresponds to

node n_3 . For this element e_1 , nodes n_4 , n_5 and n_6 do not contribute for the local stiffness matrix. Thus,

$$\mathbf{B}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.04 & 0 & 0.14 & 0 & -0.10 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -0.02 & 0 & 0.02 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.02 & -0.04 & 0.02 & 0.14 & 0 & -0.10 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (40)$$

The first 6 columns are for nodes n_1 , n_2 and n_3 , and the last 6 columns are for nodes n_4 , n_5 and n_6 . Next the material constitutive matrix can be constructed by assuming $E = Y(e_i, 1) = 210000$ and $\nu = P(e_i, 1) = 0.31$.

$$\mathbf{C}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E} & -\frac{\nu}{E} & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu}{E} & \frac{1}{E} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{2(1+\nu)}{E} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 232326 & 72021 & 0 \\ 72021 & 232326 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 80152 \end{bmatrix} \quad (41)$$

The local stiffness matrix is calculated using equation 22,

$$\mathbf{K}_1 = \mathbf{B}_1^T \cdot \mathbf{C}_1 \cdot \mathbf{B}_1 \cdot V_1 \quad (42)$$

which leads to:

$$\mathbf{K}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.2019 & 0.0609 & -0.6665 & -0.1410 & 0.4647 & 0.0802 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.0609 & 0.1106 & -0.1329 & -0.2709 & 0.0720 & 0.1603 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.6665 & -0.1329 & 2.2928 & 0.2130 & -1.6263 & -0.0802 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.1410 & -0.2709 & 0.2130 & 0.8320 & -0.0720 & -0.5611 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.4647 & 0.0720 & -1.6263 & -0.0720 & 1.1616 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.0802 & 0.1603 & -0.0802 & -0.5611 & 0 & 0.4008 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot 10^6 \quad (43)$$

It is time now to pass to the next element.

2.3.2. Element 2

Since all the important structures were already presented for element 1, the presentation can now be much swift. First, the corresponding nodes n_i , n_j and n_k forming the element are called from matrix \mathbf{e}_{mat} , by setting $e_i = 2$, because it is being calculated element 2.

$$n_i = (e_i, 1) = 2; \quad n_j = (e_i, 2) = 3; \quad n_k = (e_i, 3) = 4; \quad (44)$$

then, the nodal coordinates are recovered:

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{X}(1:3, n_i) = \begin{Bmatrix} 10 \\ 50 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}; \quad \mathbf{x}_j = \mathbf{X}(1:3, n_j) = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 70 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}; \quad \mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{X}(1:3, n_k) = \begin{Bmatrix} 30 \\ 70 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (45)$$

Afterwards, knowing that the thickness of the element is $h_e = \mathbf{h}(e_i, 1)$ the volume of the element is calculated:

$$\mathbf{v}_{ij} = \mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i; \quad \mathbf{v}_{ik} = \mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{x}_i; \quad A_e = \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{v}_{ij} \times \mathbf{v}_{ik}\|; \quad V_e = A_e \cdot h_e = 300mm^3 \quad (46)$$

which corresponds to its weight. The theoretical position of the integration point is the centre of the element:

$$\mathbf{x}_I = \frac{1}{3}(\mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{x}_j + \mathbf{x}_k) = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \left[\begin{array}{c} \begin{pmatrix} 10 \\ 50 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 70 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 30 \\ 70 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \end{array} \right] = \begin{pmatrix} 13.333 \\ 63.333 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (47)$$

then, the geometric moment matrix \mathbf{G} can be calculated using the nodal coordinates,

$$\mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_i & y_i \\ 1 & x_j & y_j \\ 1 & x_k & y_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 10 & 50 \\ 1 & 0 & 70 \\ 1 & 30 & 70 \end{bmatrix} \quad (48)$$

and its corresponding inverted version:

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{G}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} g_{11} & g_{12} & g_{13} \\ g_{21} & g_{22} & g_{23} \\ g_{31} & g_{32} & g_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 3.5000 & -1.3333 & -1.1667 \\ -0.0000 & -0.0333 & 0.0333 \\ -0.0500 & 0.0333 & 0.0167 \end{bmatrix} \quad (49)$$

The shape functions can now be calculated in any interest point inside the element using equation 6. For example, they can be calculated at the integration point:

$$\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{Bmatrix} N_i(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ N_j(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ N_k(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{Bmatrix}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.333 \\ 0.333 \\ 0.333 \end{Bmatrix}^T \quad (50)$$

More important are the partial derivatives of the shape function, that can be obtained with equation 12 and 13,

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I)}{dx} = \begin{Bmatrix} g_{21} \\ g_{22} \\ g_{23} \end{Bmatrix}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.0000 \\ -0.0333 \\ 0.0333 \end{Bmatrix}^T ; \quad \frac{d\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I)}{dy} = \begin{Bmatrix} g_{31} \\ g_{32} \\ g_{33} \end{Bmatrix}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} -0.050 \\ 0.0333 \\ 0.0167 \end{Bmatrix}^T \quad (51)$$

which allow to obtain the deformability matrix, from equation 14. Again, it is possible to arrange such deformability matrix in the global setting, knowing that node n_i corresponds to node n_2 , node n_j corresponds to node n_3 and node n_k corresponds to node n_4 . For this element e_2 , nodes n_1 , n_5 and n_6 do not contribute for the local stiffness matrix. Thus,

$$\mathbf{B}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -0.0000 & 0 & -0.0333 & 0 & 0.0333 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.0500 & 0 & 0.0333 & 0 & 0.0167 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.0500 & -0.0000 & 0.0333 & -0.0333 & 0.0167 & 0.0333 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (52)$$

The first 2 columns are for node n_1 , the next 6 columns are for nodes n_2 , n_3 and n_4 , and the last 4 columns are for nodes n_5 and n_6 . Next the material constitutive matrix can be constructed by assuming $E = Y(e_i, 1) = 70000$ and $\nu = P(e_i, 1) = 0.27$.

$$\mathbf{C}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E} & -\frac{\nu}{E} & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu}{E} & \frac{1}{E} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{2(1+\nu)}{E} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 7.5504 & 2.0386 & 0 \\ 2.0386 & 7.5504 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2.7559 \end{bmatrix} \cdot 10^4 \quad (53)$$

The local stiffness matrix is calculated using equation 22,

$$\mathbf{K}_2 = \mathbf{B}_2^T \cdot \mathbf{C}_2 \cdot \mathbf{B}_2 \cdot V_2 \quad (54)$$

which leads to:

$$\mathbf{K}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2.0669 & 0.0000 & -1.3780 & 1.3780 & -0.6890 & -1.3780 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.0000 & 5.6628 & 1.0193 & -3.7752 & -1.0193 & -1.8876 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1.3780 & 1.0193 & 3.4354 & -1.5982 & -2.0575 & 0.5789 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1.3780 & -3.7752 & -1.5982 & 3.4354 & 0.2202 & 0.3398 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.6890 & -1.0193 & -2.0575 & 0.2202 & 2.7465 & 0.7991 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1.3780 & -1.8876 & 0.5789 & 0.3398 & 0.7991 & 1.5478 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot 10^4 \quad (55)$$

It is time now to move on to the next element.

2.3.3. Element 3

First, the corresponding nodes n_i , n_j and n_k forming the element are called from matrix \mathbf{e}_{mat} , by setting $e_i = 3$, because it is being calculated element 3.

$$n_i = (e_i, 1) = 2; \quad n_j = (e_i, 2) = 4; \quad n_k = (e_i, 3) = 5; \quad (56)$$

then, the nodal coordinates are recovered:

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{X}(1 : 3, n_i) = \begin{Bmatrix} 10 \\ 50 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}; \quad \mathbf{x}_j = \mathbf{X}(1 : 3, n_j) = \begin{Bmatrix} 30 \\ 70 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}; \quad \mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{X}(1 : 3, n_k) = \begin{Bmatrix} 60 \\ 50 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (57)$$

Afterwards, knowing that the thickness of the element is $h_e = \mathbf{h}(e_i, 1)$ the volume of the element is calculated:

$$\mathbf{v}_{ij} = \mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i; \quad \mathbf{v}_{ik} = \mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{x}_i; \quad A_e = \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{v}_{ij} \times \mathbf{v}_{ik}\|; \quad V_e = A_e \cdot h_e = 500 \text{mm}^3 \quad (58)$$

which corresponds to its weight. The theoretical position of the integration point is the centre of the element:

$$\mathbf{x}_I = \frac{1}{3}(\mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{x}_j + \mathbf{x}_k) = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \left[\begin{Bmatrix} 10 \\ 50 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} 30 \\ 70 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} 60 \\ 50 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \right] = \begin{Bmatrix} 33.333 \\ 56.666 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (59)$$

then, the geometric moment matrix \mathbf{G} can be calculated using the nodal coordinates,

$$\mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_i & y_i \\ 1 & x_j & y_j \\ 1 & x_k & y_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 10 & 50 \\ 1 & 30 & 70 \\ 1 & 60 & 70 \end{bmatrix} \quad (60)$$

and its corresponding inverted version:

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{G}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} g_{11} & g_{12} & g_{13} \\ g_{21} & g_{22} & g_{23} \\ g_{31} & g_{32} & g_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2.7000 & -2.5000 & 0.8000 \\ -0.0200 & 0 & 0.0200 \\ -0.0300 & 0.0500 & -0.0200 \end{bmatrix} \quad (61)$$

The shape functions can now be calculated in any interest point inside the element using equation 6. For example, they can be calculated at the integration point:

$$\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{Bmatrix} N_i(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ N_j(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ N_k(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{Bmatrix}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.333 \\ 0.333 \\ 0.333 \end{Bmatrix}^T \quad (62)$$

More important are the partial derivatives of the shape function, that can be obtained with equation 12 and 13,

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I)}{dx} = \begin{Bmatrix} g_{21} \\ g_{22} \\ g_{23} \end{Bmatrix}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} -0.0200 \\ 0 \\ 0.0200 \end{Bmatrix}^T ; \quad \frac{d\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I)}{dy} = \begin{Bmatrix} g_{31} \\ g_{32} \\ g_{33} \end{Bmatrix}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} -0.0300 \\ 0.0500 \\ -0.0200 \end{Bmatrix}^T \quad (63)$$

which allow to obtain the deformability matrix, from equation 14. Again, it is possible to arrange such deformability matrix in the global setting, knowing that node n_i corresponds to node n_2 , node n_j corresponds to node n_4 and node n_k corresponds to node n_5 . For this element e_3 , nodes n_1 , n_3 and n_6 do not contribute for the local stiffness matrix. Thus,

$$\mathbf{B}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -0.0200 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0200 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.0300 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0500 & 0 & -0.0200 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.0300 & -0.0200 & 0 & 0 & 0.0500 & 0 & -0.0200 & 0.0200 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (64)$$

The first 2 columns are for node n_1 , the next 2 columns are for nodes n_2 , the next 2 columns are for node n_3 , the next four columns are for nodes n_4 and n_5 , and the last 2 columns are for node n_6 . Next the material constitutive matrix can be constructed by assuming $E = Y(e_i, 1) = 70000$ and $\nu = P(e_i, 1) = 0.27$.

$$\mathbf{C}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E} & -\frac{\nu}{E} & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu}{E} & \frac{1}{E} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{2(1+\nu)}{E} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 7.5504 & 2.0386 & 0 \\ 2.0386 & 7.5504 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2.7559 \end{bmatrix} \cdot 10^4 \quad (65)$$

The local stiffness matrix is calculated using equation 22,

$$\mathbf{K}_3 = \mathbf{B}_3^T \cdot \mathbf{C}_3 \cdot \mathbf{B}_3 \cdot V_3 \quad (66)$$

which leads to:

$$\mathbf{K}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2.7502 & 1.4384 & 0 & 0 & -2.0669 & -1.0193 & -0.6833 & -0.4190 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1.4384 & 3.9489 & 0 & 0 & -1.3780 & -5.6628 & -0.0604 & 1.7139 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -2.0669 & -1.3780 & 0 & 0 & 3.4449 & 0 & -1.3780 & 1.3780 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1.0193 & -5.6628 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 9.4380 & 1.0193 & -3.7752 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.6833 & -0.0604 & 0 & 0 & -1.3780 & 1.0193 & 2.0613 & -0.9589 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.4190 & 1.7139 & 0 & 0 & 1.3780 & -3.7752 & -0.9589 & 2.0613 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot 10^4 \quad (67)$$

It is time now to move on to the last element.

2.3.4. Element 4

First, the corresponding nodes n_i , n_j and n_k forming the element are called from matrix \mathbf{e}_{mat} , by setting $e_i = 4$, because it is being calculated element 4.

$$n_i = (e_i, 1) = 4; \quad n_j = (e_i, 2) = 5; \quad n_k = (e_i, 3) = 6; \quad (68)$$

then, the nodal coordinates are recovered:

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{X}(1:3, n_i) = \begin{Bmatrix} 30 \\ 70 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{x}_j = \mathbf{X}(1:3, n_j) = \begin{Bmatrix} 60 \\ 50 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{X}(1:3, n_k) = \begin{Bmatrix} 60 \\ 70 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (69)$$

Afterwards, knowing that the thickness of the element is $h_e = \mathbf{h}(e_i, 1)$ the volume of the element is calculated:

$$\mathbf{v}_{ij} = \mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i \quad ; \quad \mathbf{v}_{ik} = \mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{x}_i \quad ; \quad A_e = \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{v}_{ij} \times \mathbf{v}_{ik}\| \quad ; \quad V_e = A_e \cdot h_e = 300\text{mm}^3 \quad (70)$$

which corresponds to its weight. The theoretical position of the integration point is the centre of the element:

$$\mathbf{x}_I = \frac{1}{3}(\mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{x}_j + \mathbf{x}_k) = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \left[\begin{Bmatrix} 10 \\ 50 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} 30 \\ 70 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} 60 \\ 50 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \right] = \begin{Bmatrix} 50 \\ 63.333 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (71)$$

then, the geometric moment matrix \mathbf{G} can be calculated using the nodal coordinates,

$$\mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_i & y_i \\ 1 & x_j & y_j \\ 1 & x_k & y_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 30 & 70 \\ 1 & 60 & 50 \\ 1 & 60 & 70 \end{bmatrix} \quad (72)$$

and its corresponding inverted version:

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{G}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} g_{11} & g_{12} & g_{13} \\ g_{21} & g_{22} & g_{23} \\ g_{31} & g_{32} & g_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2.0000 & 3.5000 & -4.5000 \\ -0.0333 & 0 & 0.0333 \\ 0 & -0.0500 & 0.0500 \end{bmatrix} \quad (73)$$

The shape functions can now be calculated in any interest point inside the element using equation 6. For example, they can be calculated at the integration point:

$$\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{Bmatrix} N_i(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ N_j(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ N_k(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{Bmatrix}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.333 \\ 0.333 \\ 0.333 \end{Bmatrix}^T \quad (74)$$

More important are the partial derivatives of the shape function, that can be obtained with equation 12 and 13,

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I)}{dx} = \begin{Bmatrix} g_{21} \\ g_{22} \\ g_{23} \end{Bmatrix}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} -0.0333 \\ 0 \\ 0.0333 \end{Bmatrix}^T \quad ; \quad \frac{d\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_I)}{dy} = \begin{Bmatrix} g_{31} \\ g_{32} \\ g_{33} \end{Bmatrix}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ -0.0500 \\ -0.0500 \end{Bmatrix}^T \quad (75)$$

which allow to obtain the deformability matrix, from equation 14. Again, it is possible to arrange such deformability matrix in the global setting, knowing that node n_i corresponds to node n_4 , node n_j corresponds to node n_5 and node n_k corresponds to node n_6 . For this element e_3 , nodes n_1 , n_2 and n_3 do not contribute for the local stiffness matrix. Thus,

$$\mathbf{B}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.0333 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0333 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.0500 & 0 & 0.0500 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.0333 & -0.0500 & 0 & 0.0500 & 0.0333 \end{bmatrix} \quad (76)$$

The first 6 columns are for node n_1 , n_2 , n_3 , and the next 6 columns are for nodes n_4 , n_5 and n_6 . Next the material constitutive matrix can be constructed by assuming $E = Y(e_i, 1) = 70000$ and $\nu = P(e_i, 1) = 0.27$.

$$\mathbf{C}_4 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E} & -\frac{\nu}{E} & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu}{E} & \frac{1}{E} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{2(1+\nu)}{E} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 7.5504 & 2.0386 & 0 \\ 2.0386 & 7.5504 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2.7559 \end{bmatrix} \cdot 10^4 \quad (77)$$

The local stiffness matrix is calculated using equation 22,

$$\mathbf{K}_4 = \mathbf{B}_4^T \cdot \mathbf{C}_4 \cdot \mathbf{B}_4 \cdot V_4 \quad (78)$$

which leads to:

$$\mathbf{K}_4 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2.5168 & 0 & 0 & 1.0193 & -2.5168 & -1.0193 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.9186 & 1.3780 & 0 & -1.3780 & -0.9186 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.3780 & 2.0669 & 0 & -2.0669 & -1.3780 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.0193 & 0 & 0 & 5.6628 & -1.0193 & -5.6628 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -2.5168 & -1.3780 & -2.0669 & -1.0193 & 4.5837 & 2.3973 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1.0193 & -0.9186 & -1.3780 & -5.6628 & 2.3973 & 6.5815 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot 10^4 \quad (79)$$

2.4. Global stiffness matrix

Since all local matrices are already in the global format (they all contain the information regarding all nodes and corresponding degrees of freedom), the assemblage of the global stiffness matrix is a straightforward procedure:

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{K}_1 + \mathbf{K}_2 + \mathbf{K}_3 + \mathbf{K}_4 \quad (80)$$

leading to:

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.2019 & 0.0609 & -0.6665 & -0.1410 & 0.4647 & 0.0802 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.0609 & 0.1106 & -0.1329 & -0.2709 & 0.0720 & 0.1603 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.6665 & -0.1329 & 2.3410 & 0.2274 & -1.6401 & -0.0664 & -0.0276 & -0.0240 & -0.0068 & -0.0042 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.1410 & -0.2709 & 0.2274 & 0.9281 & -0.0618 & -0.5988 & -0.0240 & -0.0755 & -0.0006 & 0.0171 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.4647 & 0.0720 & -1.6401 & -0.0618 & 1.1960 & -0.0160 & -0.0206 & 0.0058 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.0802 & 0.1603 & -0.0664 & -0.5988 & -0.0160 & 0.4351 & 0.0022 & 0.0034 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.0276 & -0.0240 & -0.0206 & 0.0022 & 0.0871 & 0.0080 & -0.0138 & 0.0240 & -0.0252 & -0.0102 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.0240 & -0.0755 & -0.0058 & 0.0034 & 0.0080 & 0.1190 & 0.0240 & -0.0378 & -0.0138 & -0.0092 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.0068 & -0.0006 & 0 & 0 & -0.0138 & 0.0240 & 0.0413 & -0.0096 & -0.0207 & -0.0138 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.0042 & 0.0171 & 0 & 0 & 0.0240 & -0.0378 & -0.0096 & 0.0772 & -0.0102 & -0.0566 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.0252 & -0.0138 & -0.0207 & -0.0102 & 0.0458 & 0.0240 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.0102 & -0.0092 & -0.0138 & -0.0566 & 0.0240 & 0.0658 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot 10^6 \quad (81)$$

2.5. Global force vector

Regarding the external forces, there are two kinds of forces involved in this example. A concentrated force of 30N and a distributed force of 10N/mm. Thus, node n_3 has, in its O_x degree of freedom a positive force of $F_1 = 30N$. Then, the linear elements formed by nodes n_3 , n_4 and n_6 have a distributed force of $q = 10N/mm$ acting along their O_y degree of freedom in the negative direction. It would be necessary to numerically integrate the external force along the linear elements formed by nodes n_3 , n_4 and n_5 . However, such task is beyond the scope of the present paper, and the integration will be performed "manually", as shown in figure 5.

The linear element, of length 30mm, formed by nodes n_3 and n_4 has a distributed force of 10N/mm, which means that this element is under a total load of: $F_{e1} = 30mm \times 10N/mm = 300N$. Dividing this load to each node, node n_3 supports 150N and node n_4 supports the other 150N, both along the negative direction O_y . This will be called load F_2 . Repeating the process for the linear element, of length 30mm, formed by nodes n_4 and n_6 , this element is under a total load of: $F_{e2} = 30mm \times 10N/mm = 300N$. Again, dividing this load to each node, node n_4 supports 150N and node n_6 supports the other 150N, both along the negative direction O_y . This will be called load F_3 . Thus, the global force vector can be written as:

Figure 5. Swhift procedure to obtain the nodal forces from a distributed force.

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_1 + \mathbf{F}_2 + \mathbf{F}_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 30 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -150 \\ 0 \\ -150 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -150 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -150 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 30 \\ -150 \\ 0 \\ -300 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -150 \end{pmatrix} \quad (82)$$

2.6. Imposing the essential boundary conditions

Both global stiffness matrix and force vectors are defined. Now, it is necessary to impose in the system of equation the essential boundary conditions - the constraint displacements. Observing the problem, it is possible to visualize that node n_1 is blocked along Ox and Oy directions, which means that $\bar{u}_1 = 0$ and $\bar{v}_1 = 0$. Since both \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{F} are organized with the following order: $\{u_1, v_1, u_2, v_2, u_3, v_3, u_4, v_4, u_5, v_5, u_6, v_6\}$, the first two rows of \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{F} must be intervened. Then, it is also possible to visualize that nodes n_5 and n_6 have their Ox degree of freedom blocked: $\bar{u}_5 = 0$ and $\bar{u}_6 = 0$. Thus, the 9th and the 11th row have to be intervened, because these are the rows corresponding to the degree of freedom Ox of nodes n_5 and n_6 , respectively. Thus, following the procedure indicated in equations 26 and 27, it is possible to impose the essential boundary conditions:

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.6665 & -0.1329 & 2.3410 & 0.2274 & -1.6401 & -0.0664 & -0.0276 & -0.0240 & -0.0068 & -0.0042 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.1410 & -0.2709 & 0.2274 & 0.9281 & -0.0618 & -0.5988 & -0.0240 & -0.0755 & -0.0006 & 0.0171 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.4647 & 0.0720 & -1.6401 & -0.0618 & 1.1960 & -0.0160 & -0.0206 & 0.0058 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.0802 & 0.1603 & -0.0664 & -0.5988 & -0.0160 & 0.4351 & 0.0022 & 0.0034 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.0276 & -0.0240 & -0.0206 & 0.0022 & 0.0871 & 0.0080 & -0.0138 & 0.0240 & -0.0252 & -0.0102 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.0240 & -0.0755 & 0.0058 & 0.0034 & 0.0080 & 0.1190 & 0.0240 & -0.0378 & -0.0138 & -0.0092 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.0042 & 0.0171 & 0 & 0 & 0.0240 & -0.0378 & -0.0096 & 0.0772 & -0.0102 & -0.0566 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.0102 & -0.0092 & -0.0138 & -0.0566 & 0.0240 & 0.0658 \end{bmatrix} \cdot 10^6 \quad (83)$$

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{pmatrix} \bar{u}_1 \\ \bar{v}_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 30 \\ -150 \\ 0 \\ -300 \\ \bar{u}_5 \\ 0 \\ \bar{u}_6 \\ -150 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 30 \\ -150 \\ 0 \\ -300 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -150 \end{pmatrix} \quad (84)$$

In this application example, all the displacement constraints are null. However, they can be different from zero. In that case, the global force vector would be formed by loads and displacements.

2.7. Solving the system of equations

The displacement field is obtained by solving the system of equations:

$$\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{K}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{F} = \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ v_1 \\ u_2 \\ v_2 \\ u_3 \\ v_3 \\ u_4 \\ v_4 \\ u_5 \\ v_5 \\ u_6 \\ v_6 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0.0007 \\ -0.0134 \\ 0.0004 \\ -0.0185 \\ 0.0075 \\ -0.0296 \\ 0 \\ -0.0478 \\ 0 \\ -0.0464 \end{pmatrix} [mm] \quad (85)$$

Adding the displacement field to the nodal coordinates it is possible to visualize the deformed configuration, figure 6.

2.8. Strain field

It is possible to calculate the strain field for each element using equation 11.

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{(e1)} = \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{pmatrix}_{(e1)} = \mathbf{B}_1 \cdot \mathbf{d} = \begin{pmatrix} 0.0665 \\ -0.2688 \\ -0.0146 \end{pmatrix} \cdot 10^{-3} \quad (86)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{(e2)} = \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{pmatrix}_{(e2)} = \mathbf{B}_2 \cdot \mathbf{d} = \begin{pmatrix} 0.2388 \\ -0.4390 \\ -0.2690 \end{pmatrix} \cdot 10^{-3} \quad (87)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{(e3)} = \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{pmatrix}_{(e3)} = \mathbf{B}_3 \cdot \mathbf{d} = \begin{pmatrix} -0.0148 \\ -0.1222 \\ -0.3322 \end{pmatrix} \cdot 10^{-3} \quad (88)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{(e4)} = \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{pmatrix}_{(e4)} = \mathbf{B}_4 \cdot \mathbf{d} = \begin{pmatrix} -0.2512 \\ 0.0711 \\ -0.5578 \end{pmatrix} \cdot 10^{-3} \quad (89)$$

Figure 6. Initial configuration in black and deformed configuration in blue. The deformed configuration was magnified with a factor of $100\times$.

Figure 7. Strain fields.

In figure 7 it is represented the obtained strain field. The lack of detail is related with the low number of nodes used in the discretization. If more nodes were used, a more detailed mapping would be obtained.

2.9. Stress field

It is possible to calculate the stress field for each element using equation 3.

$$\sigma_{(e1)} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}_{(e1)} = \mathbf{D}_1 \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{(e1)} = \begin{Bmatrix} -3.8983 \\ -57.6533 \\ -1.1734 \end{Bmatrix} [MPa] \quad (90)$$

$$\sigma_{(e2)} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}_{(e2)} = \mathbf{D}_2 \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{(e2)} = \begin{Bmatrix} 9.0788 \\ -28.2794 \\ -7.4126 \end{Bmatrix} [MPa] \quad (91)$$

$$\sigma_{(e3)} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}_{(e3)} = \mathbf{D}_3 \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{(e3)} = \begin{Bmatrix} -3.6101 \\ -9.5285 \\ -9.1549 \end{Bmatrix} [MPa] \quad (92)$$

$$\sigma_{(e4)} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}_{(e4)} = \mathbf{D}_4 \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{(e4)} = \begin{Bmatrix} -17.5147 \\ 0.2491 \\ -15.3737 \end{Bmatrix} [MPa] \quad (93)$$

Figure 8. Stress fields.

In figure 8 it is represented the obtained stress field. Again, the lack of detail is related with the low number of nodes used in the discretization. If more nodes were used, a more detailed representation would be obtained.

3. OCTAVE/MATLAB CODE

In order to assist the understanding of the FEM procedure, the following Octave/Matlab code is delivered for the 2D examples shown in section 2.

```

1 clear all
2 close all
3 % a - nodal matrix
4 x = [
5 10 10 0 30 60 60
6 0 50 70 70 50 70
7 0 0 0 0 0 0];
8 % b - element matrix
9 e_mat = [
10 1 2 3
11 2 3 4
12 2 4 5
13 4 5 6];
14 % c, d, e, f,
15 %material properties and thickness of each element (4 elements)
16 Y=[ 210000 70000 70000 70000]';
17 P=[ 0.31 0.27 0.27 0.27 ]';
18 h=[ 2 1 1 1 ]';
19 % ***** element - e1
20 ei = 1; % element 1
21 ni = e_mat(ei,1);
22 nj = e_mat(ei,2);
23 nk = e_mat(ei,3);
24 xi=x(1:3,ni);
25 xj=x(1:3,nj);
26 xk=x(1:3,nk);
27 vij=xj-xi;
28 vik=xk-xi;
29 area = 1/2 * norm(cross(vij,vik)); % area
30 V1 = h(ei,1) * area; % volume
31 xI(1:3,1) = (xi+xj+xk)/3;
32 % shape functions:
33 G_mat = [1 xi(1,1) xi(2,1);
34           1 xj(1,1) xj(2,1);
35           1 xk(1,1) xk(2,1)];
36 g=G_mat^-1;
37 % material constitutive matrix:
38 EE=Y(ei,1);
39 nu=P(ei,1);
40 D1 = [ 1/EE -nu/EE 0 ;
41        -nu/EE 1/EE 0 ;
42        0 0 2*(1+nu)/EE ]^(-1);

```

```

43 % shape functions:
44 N = [1 xI(1,1) xI(2,1)] * g;
45 % partial derivatives:
46 dNidx = g(2,1);
47 dNidy = g(3,1);
48 dNjdx = g(2,2);
49 dNjdy = g(3,2);
50 dNkdx = g(2,3);
51 dNkdy = g(3,3);
52 % deformability matrix (nodes 123):
53 B1 = [ dNidx 0          dNjdx 0          dNkdx 0          0 0          0 0          0 0 ;
54        0          dNidy 0          dNjdy 0          dNkdy 0          0 0          0 0          0 0 ;
55        dNidy dNidx  dNjdy dNjdx  dNkdy dNkdx  0 0          0 0          0 0 ];
56 % stiffness matrix
57 K1 = B1' * D1 * B1 * V1;
58 % ***** element - e2
59 ei = 2; % element 2
60 ni = e_mat(ei,1);
61 nj = e_mat(ei,2);
62 nk = e_mat(ei,3);
63 xi=x(1:3,ni);
64 xj=x(1:3,nj);
65 xk=x(1:3,nk);
66 vij=xj-xi;
67 vik=xk-xi;
68 area = 1/2 * norm(cross(vij,vik)); % area
69 V2 = h(ei,1) * area; % volume
70 xI(1:3,1) = (xi+xj+xk)/3;
71 % shape functions:
72 G_mat = [1 xi(1,1) xi(2,1);
73          1 xj(1,1) xj(2,1);
74          1 xk(1,1) xk(2,1)];
75 g=G_mat^-1;
76 % material constitutive matrix:
77 EE=Y(ei,1);
78 nu=P(ei,1);
79 D2 = [ 1/EE -nu/EE 0 ;
80        -nu/EE 1/EE 0 ;
81        0 0 2*(1+nu)/EE ]^(-1);
82 % shape functions:
83 N = [1 xI(1,1) xI(2,1)] * g;
84 % partial derivatives:
85 dNidx = g(2,1);
86 dNidy = g(3,1);
87 dNjdx = g(2,2);
88 dNjdy = g(3,2);
89 dNkdx = g(2,3);
90 dNkdy = g(3,3);
91 % deformability matrix (nodes 234):
92 B2 = [ 0 0          dNidx 0          dNjdx 0          dNkdx 0          0 0          0 0 ;
93        0 0          0          dNidy 0          dNjdy 0          dNkdy 0          0 0          0 0 ;
94        0 0          dNidy dNidx  dNjdy dNjdx  dNkdy dNkdx  0 0          0 0 ];
95 % stiffness matrix
96 K2 = B2' * D2 * B2 * V2;
97 % ***** element - e3
98 ei = 3; % element 3
99 ni = e_mat(ei,1);
100 nj = e_mat(ei,2);
101 nk = e_mat(ei,3);
102 xi=x(1:3,ni);
103 xj=x(1:3,nj);
104 xk=x(1:3,nk);
105 vij=xj-xi;
106 vik=xk-xi;
107 area = 1/2 * norm(cross(vij,vik)); % area
108 V3 = h(ei,1) * area; % volume
109 xI(1:3,1) = (xi+xj+xk)/3;
110 % shape functions:
111 G_mat = [1 xi(1,1) xi(2,1);
112          1 xj(1,1) xj(2,1);
113          1 xk(1,1) xk(2,1)];

```

```

114 g=G_mat^-1;
115 % material constitutive matrix:
116 EE=Y(ei,1);
117 nu=P(ei,1);
118 D3 = [ 1/EE -nu/EE 0 ;
119        -nu/EE 1/EE 0 ;
120         0 0 2*(1+nu)/EE ]^(-1);
121 % shape functions:
122 N = [1 xI(1,1) xI(2,1)] * g;
123 % partial derivatives
124 dNidx = g(2,1);
125 dNidy = g(3,1);
126 dNjdx = g(2,2);
127 dNjdy = g(3,2);
128 dNkdx = g(2,3);
129 dNkdy = g(3,3);
130 % deformability matrix (nodes 245):
131 B3 = [ 0 0 dNidx 0 0 0 dNjdx 0 dNkdx 0 0 0 ;
132        0 0 0 dNidy 0 0 0 dNjdy 0 dNkdy 0 0 ;
133        0 0 dNidy dNidx 0 0 dNjdy dNjdx dNkdy dNkdx 0 0 ];
134 % stiffness matrix
135 K3 = B3' * D3 * B3 * V3;
136 % ***** element - e4
137 ei = 4; % element 4
138 ni = e_mat(ei,1);
139 nj = e_mat(ei,2);
140 nk = e_mat(ei,3);
141 xi=x(1:3,ni);
142 xj=x(1:3,nj);
143 xk=x(1:3,nk);
144 vij=xj-xi;
145 vik=xk-xi;
146 area = 1/2 * norm(cross(vij,vik)); % area
147 V4 = h(ei,1) * area; % volume
148 xI(1:3,1) = (xi+xj+xk)/3;
149 % shape functions:
150 G_mat = [1 xi(1,1) xi(2,1);
151           1 xj(1,1) xj(2,1);
152           1 xk(1,1) xk(2,1)];
153 g=G_mat^-1;
154 % material constitutive matrix:
155 EE=Y(ei,1);
156 nu=P(ei,1);
157 D4 = [ 1/EE -nu/EE 0 ;
158        -nu/EE 1/EE 0 ;
159         0 0 2*(1+nu)/EE ]^(-1);
160 % shape functions:
161 N = [1 xI(1,1) xI(2,1)] * g;
162 % partial derivatives:
163 dNidx = g(2,1);
164 dNidy = g(3,1);
165 dNjdx = g(2,2);
166 dNjdy = g(3,2);
167 dNkdx = g(2,3);
168 dNkdy = g(3,3);
169 % deformability matrix (nodes 456):
170 B4 = [ 0 0 0 0 0 0 dNidx 0 dNjdx 0 dNkdx 0 ;
171        0 0 0 0 0 0 0 dNidy 0 dNjdy 0 dNkdy ;
172        0 0 0 0 0 0 dNidy dNidx dNjdy dNjdx dNkdy dNkdx ];
173 % stiffness matrix
174 K4 = B4' * D4 * B4 * V4;
175 % ***** global stiffness matrix
176 KG = K1 + K2 + K3 + K4;
177 % global force vector:
178 FG=[ 0 0 0 0 30 -150 0 -300 0 0 0 -150 ]';
179 % imposing the essential boundary conditions:
180 KC=KG;
181 KC(1,:)=0;
182 KC(1,1)=1;
183 KC(2,:)=0;
184 KC(2,2)=1;

```

```

185 KC(9,:) = 0;
186 KC(9,9) = 1;
187 KC(11,:) = 0;
188 KC(11,11) = 1;
189 FC = FG;
190 FC(1,1) = 0;
191 FC(2,1) = 0;
192 FC(9,1) = 0;
193 FC(11,1) = 0;
194 % displacement field:
195 U = KC^-1 * FC;
196 % strain and stress fields:
197 strain_1 = B1*U;
198 strain_2 = B2*U;
199 strain_3 = B3*U;
200 strain_4 = B4*U;
201 stress_1 = D1*B1*U;
202 stress_2 = D2*B2*U;
203 stress_3 = D3*B3*U;
204 stress_4 = D4*B4*U;
205 % ***** plotting the displacement
206 fact_mag = 1e2;
207 figure(1)
208 hold on
209 triplot(e_mat , x(1,:), x(2,:), 'k' )
210 triplot(e_mat , x(1,:)+fact_mag *U(1:2:length(U))', x(2,:)+fact_mag *U(2:2:
    length(U))' )
211 axis equal
212 hold off
213 % ***** plotting the stress
214 stress_v = [ stress_1 stress_2 stress_3 stress_4 ];
215 figure(2)
216 ax(1) = subplot (221);
217 trisurf(e_mat, x(1,:), x(2,:), x(3,:), stress_v(1,:))
218 axis equal; colorbar; view(2)
219 ax(2) = subplot (222);
220 trisurf(e_mat, x(1,:), x(2,:), x(3,:), stress_v(2,:))
221 axis equal; colorbar; view(2)
222 ax(3) = subplot (223);
223 trisurf(e_mat, x(1,:), x(2,:), x(3,:), stress_v(3,:))
224 axis equal; colorbar; view(2)
225 % ***** plotting the strain
226 strain_v = [ strain_1 strain_2 strain_3 strain_4 ];
227 figure(3)
228 ax(1) = subplot (321);
229 trisurf(e_mat, x(1,:), x(2,:), x(3,:), strain_v(1,:))
230 axis equal; colorbar; view(2)
231 ax(2) = subplot (322);
232 trisurf(e_mat, x(1,:), x(2,:), x(3,:), strain_v(2,:))
233 axis equal; colorbar; view(2)
234 ax(3) = subplot (323);
235 trisurf(e_mat, x(1,:), x(2,:), x(3,:), strain_v(3,:))
236 axis equal; colorbar; view(2)

```

Listing 1: Example of a FEM 2D elasticity code

4. CONVERGENCE

It is necessary to comprehend that FEM, being a discrete numerical technique based on a weak formulation, strongly depends on the mesh quality and density. If stress concentrations are expected in a given area of a structure, it is necessary to increase the nodal density on such area. Additionally, the solution obtained with FEM is always an approximated solution, that converges to a final converged solution. However, if the solution is not contained into the FEM shape function, it is not possible to reach that final converged solution. To illustrate these two concepts, consider the example of figure 1. The domain will be discretized into increasingly denser meshes, as figure 9 shows, and maintaining the triangular element of 3-nodes.

Figure 9. Mesh discretization. (a) 9 nodes. (b) 24 nodes. (c) 70 nodes. (d) 235 nodes. (e) 854 nodes. (f) 3248 nodes.

Then, assuming the same material properties of table I and corresponding locations of figure 1, the same load cases and displacement constraints are considered. Analysing each mesh with FEM, and documenting the obtained vertical displacement of point with coordinates $\mathbf{x}_6 = \{60, 70, 0\}^T$, it is possible to plot the graph of figure 10(a). It is possible to visualize that the value of v_6 for the mesh with 9 nodes is very close with the value shown in equation 85, however that value for the mesh with 9 nodes ($v_6 = -0.053\text{mm}$) is very different from the value obtained with the mesh with 3248 nodes ($v_6 = -0.3818\text{mm}$). The graph also shows that the solution has not reached the converged solution yet, which will be somewhere close to -0.40mm . Notice that the solution obtained with the mesh of 6 nodes, equation 85, is $v_6 = -0.0464\text{mm}$, which is almost only 10% of the converged value (i.e., very different values). Regarding the stress, the normal stress σ_{xx} of the triangular element containing the node with coordinates $\mathbf{x}_6 = \{60, 70, 0\}^T$ is plotted in the graph of figure 10(b). Again it is possible to visualize that the solution tends to a final converged value, but the solution is not there yet. Notice that the value of the normal stress of the initial analysis, with only 6 nodes, was $\sigma_{xx} = -17.5147\text{ MPa}$, and that the normal stress obtained with the mesh of 3248 nodes is: -182.9611 MPa , i.e., 10 times higher.

The variable fields are also less accurate for meshes with low density. Thus, in FEM, the variable field becomes more and more detail with the increasingly discretization density. Stress concentrations can be spotted and more accurate stress distributions can be observed. In figure 11 the normal stress σ_{xx} stress distributions are shown just for the material zones corresponding to elements 2, 3 and 4 of figure 1, i.e., only for the elements belonging to material 2.

Notice that for the low-density meshes (9 and 24 nodes) it is hard to understand how stress distributes within the solid. Such distribution only starts to become perceptible for the 70 nodes mesh. With the high density meshes all the relevant stress zones appear

Figure 10. Convergence study. (a) vertical displacement of node 6, v_6 with respect the number of nodes of the discretization. (b) normal stress σ_{xx} of the element containing node 6, v_6 with respect the number of nodes of the discretization.

Figure 11. Normal stress σ_{xx} distribution for the following meshes: (a) 9 nodes. (b) 24 nodes. (c) 70 nodes. (d) 235 nodes. (e) 854 nodes. (f) 3248 nodes. All the values are in MPa.

clearly: the maximum and minimum stress values at the boundary $x = 60\text{mm}$; and the stress concentration point at $x = 10\text{mm}$ and $y = 50\text{mm}$.

This examples shows that, for a FEM analysis, before assuming that a obtained value (or field distribution) is sufficiently accurate, it is necessary to perform a preliminary convergence test first. Testing if for increasingly denser nodal meshes the solution changes significantly or not is crucial. Also, if the solid possesses zones of abrupt discontinuity, it is necessary to refine the mesh at those zones, in order to capture an accurate stress field.

5. FINAL REMARKS

The finite element method (FEM) is a widely used discretization technique in computational mechanics. The full comprehension of the theoretical procedure helps understand standard commercial packages. It is important that undergraduate students in mechanical engineering, and related scientific areas, are capable to mentally visualize the complete FEM procedure. Additionally, it is necessary to comprehend that FEM is an approximation numerical technique. The solutions obtained with FEM are only approximated solutions, depending on the mesh density. Thus, it is always necessary to test which mesh density is adequate for the problem in hands. Stress concentration zones are also another relevant topic. In those zones of the model, the mesh should be refined, aiming to obtain the most accurate stress field.

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